

COMPOSITE POWER PYLONS FOR HIGH VOLTAGE TRANSMISSION LINES

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Keywords: Composite structures, High voltage electricity, Finite elements, Thin-walled structures

ABSTRACT

The work carried out in this study is related to the development of a new type of power pylon structure capable of carrying high voltage electrical cables using composite laminates consisting of glass fibers and using the composite structure itself as a built-in electrical insulator. The development consists of three stages: Finite element modelling of the pylon, combined electrical-mechanical tests and real time hybrid testing of the arm. At this stage a parametric 3D model of the pylon has been created and discretised using different element types and a parametric studied has been carried on to investigate different geometry parameters and layups. The test method for conducting combined electrical and mechanical fatigue loading on coupon specimens and sub-components is now under development.

1 INTRODUCTION

This work is part of a larger project, Power Pylons of the Future, which targets a unique market opportunity for design-driven redevelopment of overhead transmission lines (OHTLs), by developing innovative, composite-based pylons which enable new, value-added designs and technical solutions.

The lattice towers, which dominate the landscape today, were developed over 70 years ago without regard to visual appearance and, recently, growing opposition to new projects with the use of traditional towers has emerged. The current technological alternative, underground cables, is 6 to 12 times more costly and only technically feasible for short distances. Consequently, TSOs (Transmission System Operators) have difficulties meeting the growing demand for development of the network related to the expansion of alternative and renewable energy solutions. New material approaches will enable innovative visual expressions and at the same time - through the integration of insulators in the pylon design - reduce the size of the pylons significantly. As a result, new OHTL construction projects, previously subject to strong community opposition, can now be realized.

Figure 1: Size comparison between traditional high voltage electrical masts and new composite design.
(Photo courtesy of Bystup)

This positive effect of new, appealing visual designs of the OHTLs has been confirmed by TSOs through a series of projects. Moreover, as the pylons are expected to be cost-comparable to traditional pylons, they will provide an alternative for only a fraction of the price for deployment scenarios, where underground cables have so far been the only alternative.

2 FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION

In order to investigate possible geometries and laminate layups a series of parametric studies have been carried out using a 3D CAD model, which has been generated using the commercial software, SolidWorks, see Figure 2, and then imported into the finite element software, ANSYS version 15.0.

Figure 2: 3D cad model of the pylon.

Different element types namely, Solid, Shell and Solid-shell elements have been employed to model the pylon. Figure 3 demonstrates each of these elements. Each of these elements has advantages and disadvantages for modelling thin-wall structures and during this study a comparison between these elements have been carried out to find the appropriate element type for the modelling the pylon structure. The shell structure is a common approach to model thin-wall structures; however as the thickness relative to the plate/shell field size increases it is more appropriate to use solid elements in order to accurately compute transverse normal and shear stresses. However if the thickness relative to the plate/shell field is small, these transverse stresses are negligible, thus using solid elements will be computationally expensive and could also lead to ill conditioning, due to large stiffnesses associated to thickness direction strain compared to stiffnesses in two other directions [1]. An alternative element combining the shell and solid elements is known as solid-shell elements which is an attempt to overcome the difficulties faced with either of previous element types.

Figure 3: Three different element types for modelling of thin-wall structures [2].

In parallel to the shell and solid models, another model has also been generated using 3D beam elements, see Figure 4. In this model the cross section properties are retrieved using a MatLab tool box, BeamSec which is based on a 2D formulation using iso-parametric elements [3], and for the simulation, a MatLab code known as MaxiFrame which has been developed at Technical University of Denmark has been utilized. This model is light and can handle the calculation of general response of the pylon with the speed which could be appropriate for real time hybrid testing.

Figure 4: 3D beam model.

3 COMBINED ELECTRICAL-MECHANICAL TESTING

Even though the material used in this project, GFRP, is not conductive, effects of applying high voltage at a magnitude of 400 kV AC along with the arising electrical stresses due to existence of void in material superimposed on the mechanical stresses arising from the structural fatigue loads, must be investigated. For this reason a test plan for the investigation of these effects is under development employing a specific setup able to applying high voltage on a test specimen while simultaneously applying mechanical fatigue loading, see Figure 5. Earlier investigations in the literatures [4,5] to address the effect of high voltage on mechanical characteristics of GFRP composites materials used in insulators are either based on study of field-failed insulators, or just by static loading of the specimen while it is subjected to electrical field. However, combined mechanical fatigue and electrical loading could result in a different estimation of the fatigue lifetime of the GFRP materials in the pylon structure, and this will be addressed in the present project by developing a new test method and methodology.

Figure 5: Schematic of combined electrical-mechanical test.

4 REAL TIME HYBRID TESTING

Hybrid simulation is a method to analyse complex structures by creating two systems which work interactively together; a physical subsystem, which represents part of the structure and forms the

experimental test and a computational subsystem that simulates rest of the structure. The link between these two subsystems is by using actuators and the feedback of the measured responses to the computer model [6]. The advantage of such a setup and test methodology is that the need for testing the whole structure will be eliminated potentially reducing time and cost. A schematic of a hybrid test is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Real time hybrid testing schematic.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Different stages of a project aimed at the development of a new composite power pylon for high voltage transmission lines have been presented. Various finite element models for parametric studies and analysis of the mechanical strains and stresses in the structure have been described. The effects of high voltage electrical fields on GFRP structures simultaneously exposed to mechanical fatigue loading will be further investigated and at the final stage of the project a real-time hybrid testing will be conducted in order to test one of the arms of the pylon.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The financial support from the **Innovation Fund Denmark** for the project “Power Pylons of the Future (PoPyFu)” (Grant 106-2013-3) are gratefully acknowledged. Special thanks to BSc student, Peter Bager Beuschau, who built the finite element models of the pylon structure in ANSYS.

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